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Megatrends and populations at risk of malaria

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Megatrends and Populations at Risk of Malaria

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DRAFT

Background

It is a tough call to predict the future. In 1982 John Naisbit published a book in the United States, "Megatrends: Ten new directions transforming our lives". The benefit of 35 years hindsight shows this to have been a surprisingly shrewd forecast. He foresaw the transition from an industrial to an information society; the growth of high tech, balanced with human responses; the dominance of the global over national economies; growing concern for the environment; decentralisation and consequent enhanced diversity. He described a number of shifts - from a dependence on institutional help towards self-help; from representational to participatory democracy; from hierarchies to networks; from the North to South (within the US); from either/or to multiple options, leading to more roles for women, flexitime working, a variety of arts, foods, television and religion.

Several groups have subsequently come up with their own megatrends. This paper draws upon some of them to consider trends which may be important for malaria control and eradication in the future - the malaria megatrends. These are big picture changes over the coming decades. Some changes will be malaria-focused, such as the development of new drugs, diagnostics, insecticides and vaccines, and strategies to use them. Some changes will be directly relevant to malaria, such as progress towards universal health care and improved access to strengthened health systems. Others will have less direct effects, such as increasing empowerment of women – especially educationally and economically, and the growing reach and capacity of information and communication technologies (ICT). Better ICT can improve access to information for communities about malaria prevention and for patients about malaria treatment; enable more robust information systems for health managers and planners; enhance access to finance for communities and patients. More fundamentally, longer-term influences of ICT on malaria risk may result from an increased ability to access information on local, national and global issues, and the improved opportunities to engage in governance processes. These more fundamental types of considerations are the focus of this paper.

Megatrends of potential relevance include population growth, urbanisation, climate change, land use change, migration and development. Review of the literature does not identify robust estimates of the effects of any of these individual factors on malaria risk. It is not, therefore, possible to generate precise quantitative forecasts of specific changes, or even to determine with confidence where populations may become newly exposed or, conversely, where a population's current malaria risk might decline.

This paper gives an overview of broad trends and provides some insights into the complexities of interactions between them.

First we consider demographic trends - including changes in the absolute numbers in populations and their age structure. As malaria control improves it is inevitable that anti-malarial immunity will fall, leaving communities at increased risk of malaria epidemics.

Growing populations need to live somewhere and the dominant trend is towards increasing urbanization. Malaria risk is generally lower within urban compared to rural settings, but

the risk is there. The second section explores various aspects of urbanisation and opportunities to engage to contain malaria risk. It draws attention to the importance of housing quality and recommends the use of a malaria lens when planning urban development. A review of the historical approaches to malaria control in cities is suggested to heighten awareness of what has been done in the past and to stimulate a renaissance of environmental control of malaria in cities.

Changes in demography and urbanisation will be associated with change in the wealth of individuals and equity across populations. These critical considerations are explored in detail in sister papers of the SAGme.

Concerns have been expressed for years about the potential of climate change to influence malaria risk. The state of the art is examined in a separate paper which draws attention not only to the direct effects on transmission dynamics of warmer or wetter weather, but also the potential for increasingly frequent extreme events to disrupt efforts to control, eliminate and eradicate malaria.

The planet is undergoing enormous changes in land use – for example associated with de- or re-forestation. The outline of a paper in preparation explores the potential of land use changes to affect malaria risk, and an associated case study on *P knowlesi* illustrates some of the key points.

Finally, we take a brief look at a large and complex topic – migration.

In each section an exploration of the general topic is presented before discussion of malaria-relevant dimensions and consideration of potential opportunities to intervene.

Demographic Trends

Demographic and related economic changes may well be the most powerful forces to act on malaria in the coming decades. The Population Division of the United Nations' Department of Economic and Social Affairs produces a report on the World's Population Prospects. This section draws heavily on the "2017 Revision" (United Nations Department of Social and Economic Affairs, 2017).

Population Growth - the big picture

The global population of 7.6bn in 2017 is set to grow to 9.8bn by 2050 and 11.2bn in 2100. Between 2017 and 2050, half of the world's population growth will occur in only nine countries (India, Nigeria, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Pakistan, Ethiopia, the United Republic of Tanzania, the United States of America, Uganda and Indonesia). More than half of the growth up to 2050 will be in Africa (Fig 1) which, against a backdrop of declining fertility and reducing rates of population growth in all other regions (Fig 2), will make Africa the main contributor to global population growth. The population of Europe is likely to start shrinking by 2020, with those of Asia and Latin America following by the middle of the century. In contrast, Nigeria's population will likely exceed that of the United States shortly before 2050, when it will become the third largest country in the world. By 2100, Africa will contribute up to 40% of the global population, close to the 43% contributed by Asia. Africa will thus play a central role in shaping the size and distribution of the world's population in the coming decades.

Figure 2: Average annual rate of population change for the world and by region, estimates, 2000-2015, and medium-variant projection, 2015-2100

Population Momentum

The global population would continue to grow even if mortality rates remain constant at 2010-2015 levels and fertility instantly equals the replacement level (i.e. the fertility rate required to stabilise the population in the long run). This is because the current age-structure of the population includes large numbers of children and young adults who will reach adulthood in future decades. The births they have will contribute to further enlarge the population, even if they have fewer children than their parents' generation. Figure 3 shows that 65% of global population growth between 2015 – 2050 will be attributable to population momentum: much of the population growth over the next few decades is already inscribed in the youthful structure of the population in 2015.

Least Developed Countries

The UN designates 47 territories as least developed countries (LDCs), 33 of which are in Africa. The population of LDCs is projected to increase from 1.0bn in 2017 to 1.9bn in 2050 and 3.2bn in 2100. Thirty three countries, mostly LDCs, are expected to at least triple their population between 2017 and 2100, including six malaria endemic countries (Angola, Burundi, Niger, Somalia, the United Republic of Tanzania and Zambia) whose populations

are expected to grow five-fold. As the 2017 Revision states, “The concentration of population growth in the poorest countries will make it harder for those governments to eradicate poverty, reduce inequality, combat hunger and malnutrition, expand and update education and health systems, improve the provision of basic services and ensure that no-one is left behind.”

Source: POPFACTS, No. 2017/4. Available at http://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/publications/pdf/popfacts/PopFacts_2017-4.pdf

Fertility

On average, approximately 2.1 births per woman are required to maintain a population in the long run. Recent decades have seen marked reductions in fertility – the average number of live births per woman. Between 1975-1980 about one quarter of the world's population lived in countries where fertility was above five births per woman: by 2010-2015 this proportion had shrunk to 8% and by 2050 no countries are expected to have this level of fertility. However, some regions are characterised by a high levels of adolescent fertility (births to women aged 15-19 years) which brings adverse health and social consequences for the mothers and their children. The adolescent birth rate in Africa was 99 per 1,000 women aged 15-19, and in Latin America and the Caribbean 67 per 1,000.

There is little data specifically on the consequences of malaria in pregnant adolescents. However it may be anticipated that the adverse effects so well documented more broadly in pregnancy – increased rates of malaria, severe malaria, pregnancy loss, still birth, maternal anaemia, low birth weight and infant mortality – will be exacerbated in younger mothers.

Life expectancy

Global life expectancy increased by 3.6 years (from 67.2 – 70.8 years) in the decade to 2010-2015. The greatest gains – 6.6yr (producing an average life expectancy of 60.2 years)- were in Africa. The increase in life expectancy in Africa in the previous decade was less than 2 years (figure 4).

Global mortality under the age of 5 years fell from 70 per 1000 live births in 2000-2005 to 48 in 2010-2015. Declines were especially large in sub-Saharan Africa (from 141 to 95 deaths per 1,000) and in LDCs (from 123 to 83 deaths per 1,000), where declines accelerated after the year 2,000. This coincided with the intense scrutiny associated with the fourth Millennium Development Goal (MDG4) and, more recently, the third Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 3).

Predictions suggest that life expectancy in Africa will increase to 71 years by 2050. Such gains will no doubt dependent on further improvements in the control of infectious and non-infectious diseases.

The Demographic Dividend

In 2017, approximately 41% of the African population was aged under 15 years, and 19% were aged between 15 – 24 years. In Latin America and the Caribbean, and in Asia, although a smaller ($\leq 25\%$) proportion of the population are aged under 15 years a similar proportion (16-17%) are aged 15 -24 years. All together, 2.9 billion people on this planet are aged under 25 years in 2017.

The proportion of children will decrease in the near future, because of falling fertility, but the number of people in the prime working groups will grow. High ratios of working to dependent populations could drive a 'demographic dividend', with the size of the dividend proportional to the number of today's children and youth who are provided with education, health services and opportunities for productive engagement in the labour force. The more the poorest countries and most disadvantaged groups within those countries are able to engage, the greater the social and economic dividends that are likely to result.

Support Ratio

A final consideration in this section is the number of workers per retiree in a society. These numbers are hard to estimate but a reasonable proxy is the number of people expected to be in each category by virtue of their age (i.e. the number aged 20-64 years divided by the number aged 65 years and over). In 2017, the support ratio in Africa was 12.9, compared with 7.4 in Asia, 7.3 in Latin America and the Caribbean, 4.6 in Oceania, 3.8 in North America and 3.3 in Europe. Japan is the country with the lowest support ratio (2.1).

The lower the support ratio the greater the difficulty a country will have to ensure a functioning health care system, adequate pensions and social protection. European and north American countries are starting to grapple with the fiscal and political pressures associated with their low support ratios and these pressures are set to intensify over the coming decades.

Implications for malaria

These demographic changes focus our attention on Africa, the heartland of malaria and where the huge demographic changes outlined above will challenge governments to provide services to their rapidly growing populations. However, the better this is accomplished, the greater the demographic dividend and economic benefits that will result. At the same time, falling support ratios in many traditional donor countries may compromise their ability and willingness to support malaria endemic countries. As countries work out how to support and nurture their young populations they must also work out how to prioritise investments in health (Agyepong I, 2017).

Over the decades of effort that are required to move from moderate malaria transmission to malaria elimination there is a risk that individuals – policy makers, politicians and the electorate – forget the public health toll of malaria. Diminishing memories of the worst effects of malaria are replaced by more visible and current public health threats. It becomes

hard to justify the continued high level investment required to interrupt malaria transmission when the public health impact has become negligible. This is a dangerous path as faltering commitment to malaria control and elimination risks the return, with a vengeance, of high level malaria transmission.

Increasing malaria vulnerability on the path to elimination

Achieving higher coverage of the malaria control tools available today will improve malaria control in at-risk populations and eliminate malaria in some places. The new diagnostics, drugs, insecticides and vaccines in today's developmental pipeline will bring further gains in malaria control. As exposure to malaria becomes less frequent, it is less likely that individuals will develop naturally-acquired immunity (NAI) and likely that those with NAI will lose it. There is thus a real risk that, on the path to malaria elimination, whole communities will become more vulnerable to malaria infection and outbreaks will occur.

Where malaria transmission is stable, even at low intensities, individuals are exposed to multiple infections and those who survive have an opportunity to acquire protective immunity (Marsh & Kinjajui, 2006). Immunity is initially acquired to the worst effects of malaria – death and severe disease. With repeated exposure people become more able to tolerate blood-stage infections, sometimes without symptoms and, eventually, may develop anti-parasite immunity which clears infections and prevents re-infection. However, NAI wanes in the absence of repeated exposure to the parasite.

The severe manifestations of malaria vary with the age of the patient which in turn varies with the intensity of transmission (Carneiro et al, 2010). Where transmission is intense the age-pattern of severe disease is shifted to the left, with young children at greatest risk of infection, severe disease and death. Common manifestations of severe disease in children include anaemia, cerebral malaria and respiratory distress. In low transmission settings older children and adults are more likely to bear the brunt of severe disease and death. Many studies have now documented the age shift in malaria risk as transmission decreases (see Fowkes *et al* for a review). Where malaria transmission is not sufficiently intense to stimulate the development of immunity there is a risk that a sporadic malaria case will rapidly spread to cause an epidemic affecting people of all ages. Manifestations of malaria in such an outbreak include severe anaemia, cerebral malaria and respiratory distress but also complications less familiar to previously endemic settings (renal failure, liver failure, bleeding problems, etc.).

It is unclear how much exposure is required to stimulate the development of protective immunity but host and parasite factors are clearly important. There is evidence, from studies of Indonesian trans-migrants where malaria-naive people of all ages moved to an area with malaria, that adults develop immunity to malaria more rapidly than children (Baird et al, 1991, 1993). It has also been proposed that submicroscopic malaria infections may play a role in maintaining an effective immune response, a phenomenon referred to as premunition. It has also been suggested that, in low transmission settings where relatively few parasite lineages exist, immunity to the circulating parasite populations may develop more rapidly than in settings with more parasite lineages (Fowkes et al, 2016).

From the above it follows that, as malaria control improves in an endemic setting, there will be a right-shift in the age pattern of malaria infection and a change in the most frequent manifestations of severe disease. The age range of those most affected will increase as the duration for which malaria has been adequately controlled increases. Accordingly, increasing malaria risk in adolescents has already been documented (Nankanbirwa et al, 2014). It is likely that, by the time malaria is eliminated in a community, some (older) adults will still have a degree of immunological memory which may help to protect them from the most severe forms of disease. Older people may therefore become increasingly important reservoirs of infection. However, as studies of long-term migrants from endemic to non-endemic settings have shown, adults will also become vulnerable to severe disease and, possibly, death (Jennings et al, 2006, Smith et al, 2008). This is because, in those who have acquired a high degree of immunity to malaria, prolonged periods without exposure leads to the loss of protection. The time required to lose one's immunological memory is unclear.

Summary

The demographic changes described above are likely to produce novel malaria risk patterns and epidemiological features:

- (i) It will be increasingly important to understand the risks of malaria in adolescent pregnancy and opportunities for its control.
- (ii) As life expectancy increases the number of older people, who have partial immunity to malaria and may still be able to tolerate malaria infection without symptoms, will increase. Older people may therefore become a particularly important reservoir of infection. Specific strategies may be required to identify and eliminate malaria infections in older people.
- (iii) As malaria control improves, the proportion of people in the community who are either malaria naive or who have lost their protective immunity will increase. There is a serious risk that any lapse in malaria control will result in large malaria outbreaks. These may be characterised by clinical episodes in people across a wide age-range experiencing disease manifestations which were not common when malaria transmission was stable. It is important to raise awareness of the risk of malaria outbreaks, an almost inevitable consequence of improved control and a sign of long-term progress towards elimination.

As Africa develops over the coming decades so should its ability to lead its battle against malaria. To accelerate progress, investments are needed in capacity strengthening – to ensure that the future staff of National Malaria Control Programmes and district medical staff have the abilities needed to control malaria. Governments of endemic countries need to take responsibility for the investments their countries need to control malaria. At the same time, strengthened and transparent governance is required to enable populations to hold their leaders accountable.

Urbanisation

The majority of the world's population already lives in cities. By 2030, 60% of the world's population is expected to live in cities, this figure rising to 66% by 2050. The population of urban areas grew by an astonishing 1 billion people between 2000 and 2014. The United Nations estimates that more than 90% of future urban population growth will be in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (UN DESA, 2014).

Cities are the engines for economic growth, responsible for over 80% of global economic activity (UN Habitat, 2011). Comparatively well resourced, cities have more health workers, financial resources and facilities, and better electricity supply, refrigeration, and supply chain management, than rural areas. High population density facilitates large-scale access to healthcare providers, medical and other products.

Cities deserve special attention for the control of communicable diseases because they also have features that make them uniquely vulnerable. High population densities mean that people can be clustered around risks. Increased mobility and contact with people can result in increased risk of disease transmission. As cities grow, so do the inequities within them. Whole sub-populations may be considerably worse off than their urban neighbours, and sometimes their rural counterparts. Large inequities affecting huge populations cause immense humanitarian suffering and compromise the ability to meet global development targets.

The very fact that urban settings are characterised by high population densities means that effective interventions and strategies may impact enormous numbers of people. WHO's 2016 "Global report on urban health: equitable, healthier cities for sustainable development" is a mine of information and insight upon which this section is largely based.

In this section we explore how cities grow, recognise the challenge of urban inequities and hidden populations, explore how to measure urban health and the data needed to monitor the size and health of urban populations. We examine what is known about malaria in cities, how to assess it and conclude by considering opportunities to enhance malaria control in the urban environment.

How cities grow

The rate of growth of many urban populations in developing countries is beyond what can feasibly be managed by many governments. For example, Lagos is now Africa's largest city, with an estimated population of close to 10 million in 2010 (UN, 2012; Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2007). This represents a 150 fold increase from the population of 25,000 in 1866 (Ayeni, 1981). From an area of less than 50 km² on Lagos Island in 1911, Lagos now extends more than 40 km north-west of Lagos Island and covers an area of close to 1000 km² (Figures 5 and 6).

Figure 5: The change in spatial extent of Lagos between 1900 and 2013. a) 1900 (18.8 km²) b) 1963 (69.9 km²) c) 1984 (198 km²) d) 2000 (280 km²) e) 2005 (334.5 km²) f) 2013 (738 km²).

Footnote to Figure 2.3: Spatial growth of Lagos metropolis 1900 – 2013 (2.2.3a – 2.2.3f) is shown in red. Blue represents water bodies. Source figures of urban extents 1900 - 2005 were geo-rectified to WGS 1884 datum and digitized on-screen in ArcGIS version 10 (ESRI, Redlands, USA). Spatial extents in 2013 derived from supervised classification of Landsat 8 satellite imagery acquired in 2013. Total surface area of the extents in each mapped year was then calculated using geometry tool in ArcGIS 10 and validated using supplementary information on areal estimates for Lagos given in [Jesani, 2010]. Data sources used: 1900 – 2000 [Jesani, 2010]; LAMATA GIS Database (<http://www.lamata-ng.com>); 2005 - 2013 [Eyoh et al., 2012].

Figure 6: Image showing aerial view of Lagos Island in (a) 1929 (b) 2010. Image sources: (a) www.nairaland.com/865653/old-lagos-pictures (accessed April 2014) (b) www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lagos (accessed April 2014).

In the face of such rapid and enormous growth, vulnerable communities tend to develop in informal settlements at the edges of the cities. They typically have substandard housing, poor access to public services and infrastructure (e.g. undrinkable water), and inadequate health service coverage. These factors all contribute to disease transmission and deterioration of health. In some settings, urban population's health outcomes are worse than their rural counterpart's.

The stretch and sprawl of a growing city is characterised by substandard housing, traffic-clogged streets, toxic air and underserved neighbourhoods. In a global sample of 120 cities measured during 1990–2000, the geographic extent of the city grew more than twice as fast as the population (Angel S, 2011). When the outward expansion outpaces population growth, settlements have lower population densities. In some cities, relatively wealthy people may occupy these lower density settlements but in others it is the poorer residents, seeking more affordable housing, who occupy the peripheral settlements. For both, the necessities of everyday life become less accessible. Public transportation, hospitals, schools, businesses, city parks and planned public spaces are all more sustainable with higher population densities. At lower densities such infrastructure - that makes up the essence of the 'urban advantage' - becomes unsustainable. Urban spaces become single-use areas – places where people live, or work, or play and access their daily needs. A 2014 study of sprawling metropolises found a negative correlation between sprawl, health and economic opportunity across 221 cities and 994 counties in the USA (Measuring Sprawl, 2014).

Slums

Rapid rates of urbanisation put pressure on local services, including health, education and environmental and housing needs. Invariably the urban poor face the greatest hardships

and often end up living in slums and informal settlements. Slums are characterised by poor housing conditions, overcrowding, lack of access to safe water and sanitation, and a lack of secure tenure. Approximately 60% of sub-Saharan Africa's urban population live in slums, a third of those in urban Asia and a fifth of those in urban Latin America and the Caribbean (Millennium Development Goals Report, 2015). This equates to over 880 million people living in slums around the world, a figure expected to reach 2 billion by 2050 (State of the world's cities, 2013). These may well be under-estimates as many poor urban households are "invisible" (see below).

People arriving in a city from rural settings often find themselves at a financial disadvantage, then become increasingly impoverished as a result of high prices for essential commodities. The rural–urban poverty gap has narrowed in many countries, including Mozambique and Uganda, between 1990 and 2010. However, part of this reduction is due to a rise in urban poverty.

A key contributor to urban poverty is the high cost of food. In South Africa, food inflation reached 16.7% between October 2007 and October 2008, compared with an overall inflation rate of 12.1%. The poorest urban households would have had to raise their incomes by at least 22% to maintain the same food basket between April 2007 and October 2008 (Frayne et al, 2010).

Equity in Cities

On average, city dwellers enjoy better health than their rural compatriots. However, within a city, large differences often exist in access to health, and to health outcomes. In 2010, a WHO-UN-Habitat report shone a light on urban health inequities (WHO, 2010) and drew attention to the large urban populations suffering substandard living conditions and adverse health outcomes. In 2012, UNICEF documented the hundreds of millions of children living in urban slums, many without access to basic services (UNICEF, 2012) despite living in close proximity to urban amenities, including health facilities. It has been said that "one of the worst places in the world to be a mother is in an urban slum" (Save the Children, 2015).

A WHO analysis of urban DHS and the Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) data from 79 countries (WHO, 2015) showed that children in the poorest fifth of urban households are twice as likely to die before their fifth birthday as children in the richest quintile.

WHO's Centre for Health Development (WHO Kobe Centre) and its network of collaborators work to understand the basis for health inequities and the interaction of social, economic, and political determinants for health.

Measuring health in cities

WHO's 2016 "Global report on urban health" computed the Urban Health Index (UHI) for 57 cities in 53 LMICs. The UHI is a composite measure of population health and inequalities

based on locally-relevant indicators which accommodate local priorities. The 2016 report included indicators such as use of solid fuels, women's education, access to water and sanitation, women's knowledge of HIV and child health service coverage. Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) data from 2003–2013 was used, where sufficient sample sizes and identifiable boundaries were available.

Several messages emerged from the analysis:

- National level wealth did not always determine conditions for health at the city level. Index values ranged from 0.94 (Yerevan, Armenia) to 0.07 (Monrovia, Liberia) with a median value of 0.44 (Harare, Zimbabwe). The median value was nearly twice as high for cities in lower-middle income countries (0.57) compared to those in low-income countries (0.29). However, there was considerable variation even among cities in low-income countries, values ranging from 0.07 for Monrovia to 0.69 for Kathmandu.
- Megacities (which have populations greater than 10 000 000) in LMICs have worse health conditions than smaller cities. The seven megacities included in the analysis had a median index of 0.43, while cities with less than 1 million people had an average index of 0.68. Among megacities, Delhi had the highest value (0.59), still lower than the average value for smaller cities, and Lagos had the lowest value (0.30).
- Conditions for health vary widely even between cities within the same geographic region. Although African cities had the lowest median value (0.32), there was substantial variation across the continent. Nairobi, Kenya had the highest index (0.69), followed by Mbabane, Swaziland and Windhoek, Namibia (both with an index of 0.63). In the LAC, values ranged from 0.15 in Port-au-Prince, Haiti to 0.81 in Bogotá, Colombia.
- The capital cities of Guinea, Liberia, and Sierra Leone, the countries most affected by the 2014 -2015 Ebola outbreak, had some of the poorest conditions for health prior to the outbreak. Based on data from 2013 and 2014, Conakry, Guinea (0.21), Monrovia, Liberia (0.07) and Freetown, Sierra Leone (0.17) were all in the bottom fifth of the cities examined.

Data – the urban uncaptured

A 2015 UN report highlighted the challenge of invisibility and inequality in the world's cities (United Nations Data Revolution Group, 2014). Poor urban households, especially in informal settlements, may fall out of the sampling frame for population surveys and therefore end up excluded from population data: they are effectively invisible. This makes it difficult to plan for equitable delivery of essential services, including primary health care; 'invisible' people and communities are unlikely to receive the health and social services they need. Exclusion of such populations in survey data also results in under appreciation of the extent of inequities.

Opportunities afforded by the data revolution can catalyse sustainable development and close gaps in access to, and coverage and use of, data. For example, UNICEF has enhanced its Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) methodology (UNICEF, 2015) to do a better job of assessing not just urban but also slum areas. The intention is to identify pockets of poverty and children's needs with more precision than would otherwise be possible with aggregated data. Routine use of equity and performance data for localized areas, including the use of spatial data analyses, enables risk-informed planning. The expectation is that appropriate presentation of relevant data will inform policy-makers, catalyse innovation and enable local advocacy efforts.

Another example comes from the Nepali NGO, the Health Research and Social Development Forum (HERD), which has tested an innovative approach to household sampling which should document people living in informal dwellings. The approach uses the WorldPop dataset as a first-stage sampling frame. WorldPop is a publicly available (<http://www.worldpop.org.uk/>) assembly of disaggregated census data and other spatial datasets, such as remotely-sensed land cover type and road network. This provides an opportunity for informal settlements to be selected in community surveys while bypassing the challenges of access to local census data. Health status is then assessed in representative samples and, for example, helps identify appropriate locations for tailored provisions in areas with large numbers of migrants.

WHO has developed a tool to support the development of local public health observatories (www.who.int/kobe_centre/measuring/urban_health_observatory/local_observatories/en/). Urban health observatories in Latin America and the United Kingdom have generated relevant, accurate, timely and accessible data, free of political interference. These have been used to inform urban health and development policies. The attention to socially determined health inequalities is a common feature of the observatories, which necessitates an intersectoral and community inclusive approach in both generating and applying the data.

Enhancing the availability, representativeness and quality of data, including technological improvements for geocoding and analysis, as well as the capacity to use the data at the local level, are key requirements for improving urban health outcomes and equity. Data can be a resource for innovation that powers sustainable development, helping governments provide better services for more people and demonstrating the health and other co-benefits generated from coordinated action across multiple sectors.

Malaria in cities

Urban environments offer favourable grounds for the spread of infectious diseases, especially in areas of high population densities with low resources, such as slums. Increased international travel and migration have resulted in cities becoming important hubs for the transmission of infectious diseases, as shown by H1N1 and Ebola virus outbreaks. Rapid urbanization can introduce diseases mostly prevalent in remote rural areas into cities.

The growth of cities has, however, been associated with reducing risks of malaria (Tatem A, 2013) and there is clear evidence that vectors are less plentiful and prevalence of infection is lower in cities than in the surrounding rural areas (Omumbo J, 2015, Govoetchan R, 2014). Nevertheless, the importance of malaria in cities is increasingly recognised (Donnelly M, 2005). Given the vast numbers of people living in cities even a low risk of urban malaria can translate into a considerable public health problem. Work is underway to describe systematically the epidemiology, ecology and transmission of malaria in seven cities in Latin America, Asia and Africa (Wilson M, 2015). A key objective in this programme is to understand the extent to which urban malaria is a result of local, urban transmission versus infections imported from surrounding rural areas.

Malaria risk in cities is characterised by marked heterogeneity in transmission and infection risk over small areas (Wilson M, 2015). A systematic review of urban malaria in sub-Saharan Africa identified the importance of manmade, urban vector breeding sites, including urban agriculture, tyre tracks, and ditches, and low socioeconomic status as significant risk factors (De Silva, 2012).

Urban agriculture - a risk factor

The potential of irrigated urban vegetable production to facilitate malaria transmission is increasingly recognised (Drechsel P, 2014; Klinkenberg E, 2008). Such developments can be an important source of livelihood and nutrition, but may also provide breeding sites for malaria vectors. In just one urban agricultural development in Accra, Ghana, 77 farmer-built shallow water reservoirs were identified (Drechsel P, 2014). Local transmission has been implicated by finding *Anopheles* species breeding and infected *Anopheles* mosquitoes resting in houses in or near urban agriculture sites (Klinkenberg E, 2008). Urban agriculture was associated with increased mosquito biting in Benin (Yadouléton A 2010) and an increase in Entomological Inoculation Rate and malaria, and associated costs, in Ghana (Obuobie et al. 2006). Urban breeding sites may be transitory in nature, posing a challenge for larval control, but assessments of host-seeking activity indicate that insecticide-treated mosquito nets should be an effective control method.

Urban farmers can cultivate all year round and generate meaningful incomes, providing them an opportunity to lift themselves out of poverty. Urban farmers can also contribute to local perishable food requirements, not being dependent on cold transport and storage facilities. Other potential benefits of urban agriculture are associated with reductions in energy, transportation, storage and packaging costs, and urban farming may help with flood control, climate change adaptation and land reclamation. The undesirable consequences of urban agriculture, including increased malaria, pesticide misuse and associated health costs, nutrient depletion and wastewater exposure, need managing but should not be allowed to undermine the benefits of urban agriculture. Many of the challenges apply similarly to rural agriculture or to other aspects of urban living.

Assessing urban malaria

A rapid urban malaria appraisal (RUMA) has been developed as a means to a cost-effective approach to assess the malaria situation in urban sub-Saharan Africa and contribute to an informed understanding of urban malaria epidemiology (Wang S, 2005). Working in Abidjan, Cote d'Ivoire; Cotonou, Benin; Dar es Salaam, Tanzania; and Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso, a 6-step process, including literature review, school parasitaemia and health facility surveys, formed the basis of an evaluation of RUMA's feasibility, consistency and usefulness. Published and unpublished (e.g. theses and statistical) reports provided insights to the malaria situation while school and health facility-based surveys generated an overview of local endemicity in different city areas. Important problems needing subsequent in-depth assessments were identified and maps of health facilities and breeding sites, though time-consuming to produce, resulted in useful visualisations. RUMA cost USD 8,500–13,000 for an initial assessment over six to ten weeks and provided an evidence base for planning control measures.

In Quibdó, Colombia, a combination of epidemiological, entomological, and parasite genotyping methods were used to characterise malaria transmission (Gómez K, 2017). Sixteen primary infections were identified using active and passive case detection. Molecular methods applied to samples from reactive case detection (RCD) identified a further 41 infections, most of which were genetically distinct from the primary cases. This indicated that the infections detected through RCD were independent occurrences and that there was little, if any, urban malaria transmission in that setting. The study also demonstrated the utility of molecular approaches to understand the epidemiology of urban malaria.

Opportunities to intervene in urban malaria

The first challenge is to know the extent of the issue. The second is to understand the reasons for urban malaria cases – the relative contribution of local transmission versus imported infections. Although urban malaria may currently be a modest contributor to the total burden of malaria disease the concern must be that, as urban populations continue to grow, so will the malaria problem. Paying specific attention to the issues in the next few years may help avert a long-term challenge to malaria elimination and eradication efforts.

Interventions against urban malaria are likely to include standard approaches to malaria control – prevention with insecticide treated mosquito nets and possibly a greater role for indoor residual spraying than in rural areas. Larval source management may also have more of a role than in rural settings. Ensuring equitable access to parasitological diagnosis and effective treatment will continue to be important. In addition to these malaria-specific measures urban malaria may be amenable to a number of more general, but potentially very powerful, approaches.

Housing

As cities expand to accommodate their growing populations, systematic steps to improve the quality of housing are likely to yield multiple health and social benefits. Limited but increasing evidence suggests that good housing can reduce malaria risk and bring potential benefits to residents of rural and urban areas.

A systematic review and meta-analysis explored the effect of modern housing on malaria risk, in comparison with traditional housing (Tusting et al, 2015). Within the 53 studies conducted between 1900 and 2013, residents of 'modern' houses had a 47% lower odds of malaria infection and a 45–65 % lower odds of clinical malaria, compared to traditional houses. However evidence was largely from observational and case-control studies and considered of low quality with a high risk of bias.

A separate analysis of representative household survey data from 21 countries, collected between 2008-2015, revealed that houses built with finished wall, roof, and floor materials were associated with a 9 – 14% reduction in the risk of malaria (Tusting L et al, 2017). Analyses adjusted for the use of insecticide treated mosquito nets (ITN), age, gender, indoor residual spraying, household wealth, and geographic cluster. The same analyses found a 15 - 16% lower risk of malaria associated with use of ITNs. Although residual confounding, especially related to household wealth, may have contributed to the findings, the authors concluded: "Housing quality is an important risk factor for malaria infection across the spectrum of malaria endemicity in sub-Saharan Africa, with a strength of association between housing quality and malaria similar to that observed between ITN use and malaria. Improved housing should be considered a promising intervention for malaria control and elimination and long-term prevention of reintroduction."

Although there is limited evidence from randomised controlled trials (e.g. Kirby M et al, 2009), it seems likely that malaria is reduced among the residents of good quality housing who also stand to benefit from many other health gains (see www.who.int/hia/housing/en/).

Multisectoralism

Malaria is associated with risk factors and impacts in multiple sectors. Education, wealth, industry and productivity are all associated with malaria in a bi-directional interplay of factors. Just as improved malaria control can improve educational outcomes, broad economic and personal wealth outcomes, changes in these domains can impact on malaria risk. It is thus important to recognise the influence on health outcomes of decisions made outside the health sector, and to work collaboratively across sectors to address the inequitable distribution of the determinants of health. Relying on health sector responses to protect against underlying determinants of ill health - such as inadequate water, sanitation, housing, education – is not a route to a permanent solution.

Cross-sectoral policies which consider health will bring benefits not only for the health sector, but co-benefits for the other sectors involved. For example, improving nutrition outcomes positively influences not only health, but also educational attainment,

employment and productivity. Urban planning, water and sanitation, transport, housing, energy, safety, and other factors can all have positive and negative health implications. Health in All Policies (HiAP) is a specific intersectoral approach to decision-making that recognizes that most public policies have the potential to influence health and health equity in positive or negative ways (Leppo K, 2013). In the process of HiAP, decision-makers in other sectors routinely consider health outcomes, including benefits, harms and health-related costs.

Using city power

Decentralization of authority in many countries is allowing city governments greater autonomy to, for example, raise revenue, develop social and economic policies and organise programmes. Because city authorities are closer to the people they serve, they can potentially collaborate more effectively across different government departments, the private sector and civil society to serve the interests of their communities. By effecting change at the local level, and given the population of cities, municipal decision makers can make a significant impact at national and global levels.

Several fora bring together leaders of cities and facilitate idea sharing and the formation of coalitions across national borders. This may help stimulate national governments to adopt new policies.

Global partnerships

Several independent organizations provide platforms for the exchange of ideas and development of alliances, with a view to creating better cities. The International Council for Local Environmental Initiatives (ICLEI - www.iclei.org/) was formed in 1989 and now connects 20% of the world's urban population. Metropolis (www.metropolis.org/), formed in 1985, has stimulated discussion on urban health equity and residents health. The Compact of Mayors (www.compactofmayors.org) was launched by the United Nations and brings together several global city networks (the Cities Climate Leadership Group (C40), the United Cities and Local Governments Network (UCLG) and the ICLEI).

In 2010, mayors from around the world adopted a call to action at the Global Forum on Urbanization and Health in Kobe, Japan. Three focus areas were agreed: evidence-based action, multisectoral coordination and community participation in decision-making. Tools to help local authorities and civil society plan action on health inequities, such as the WHO Urban Health Equity Assessment and Response Tool (Urban HEART), were introduced along with other resources.

On World AIDS Day in 2014, UNAIDS asked mayors from around the world to commit to three concrete goals by 2020 as part of the Paris Declaration. The 90–90–90 Target (90% of people living with HIV in cities know their HIV status, 90% of them receive HIV treatment, and 90% of them have a suppressed viral load) were expected to be met at the national level by 2030, but the cities' Mayors committed to fast track their efforts to achieve them by 2020.

Engaging the citizenship

The expansion, in 1869, of the electorate in British local government has been recognised as a key determinant of the subsequent improvement in mortality rates (Szreter S, 2004). This phenomenon continues to be realised today, with an appreciation that the accountability of authorities to grassroots stakeholders is vitally important.

A necessary prerequisite to effective accountability is the availability of - and access to - relevant information. Sharing quality information empowers people to participate effectively in decision-making processes. Innovations in information technology mean that government processes, which are often slow and cumbersome, are often the rate-limiting step in the provision of data to citizens. Originally driven by a commitment to transparency and accountability, citizens, public and private sectors are starting to work together to increase efficiencies. In the United States, the federal government website (Data.gov) indicates that hundreds of software applications have been created by citizens using government data. Many of the apps focus on sharing knowledge and information on public health and its determinants.

City governments, city-based institutions (such as universities) and NGOs can play an important role in empowering citizens with information. Twaweza (www.twaweza.org), an NGO working in Kenya, Uganda and the United Republic of Tanzania, focuses on facilitating access to information and stimulating discussion, encouraging people to speak out and act to make a difference. Such an approach can help governments to get better at doing things while supporting the broader agenda of community development and empowerment.

Public-private partnerships

The private sector can contribute to the development of urban health in three main ways. Firstly, by building infrastructure and providing services, in partnership with the public sector. Secondly, by building on the comparative advantages of the private sector (e.g. marketing, supply chain management) to support the adoption of health-promoting behaviours and access to products. Thirdly, the private sector can act as a donor or philanthropist, supporting initiatives relevant to public health. Recognising that the private sector and the communities it interacts with share values can be a route to economic success and social improvement.

Summary

In the face of massive urban expansion, and the growing inequities associated with urban living, it is important to recognise the potential challenges and opportunities for malaria control and elimination afford by cities.

It will be important better to understand malaria risks in individual cities and the local heterogeneities that exist. Ensuring that 'invisible' communities are adequately represented is needed to ensure that the true extent of the malaria - and other - problems is not under-estimated. The use of specific approaches to understand malaria risk will enable the targeting of conventional approaches to malaria control. Ensuring that communities and decision-makers both have access to information, as part of an urban data revolution, will help get things done. In addition, networks which link the governors of cities within and across national boundaries can provide an opportunity to share novel strategies which impact the lives of the hundreds of millions of people living in cities.

At the same time we should not forget the lessons of the past. A detailed review of historical approaches to urban malaria control is warranted (Snow R, personal communication).

Particular attention is needed to the needs of the urban poor and the nearly one billion people living in slums and informal settlements today, and projected to double by 2050,

Cities are poised to play a leading role in addressing major global challenges of the 21st century, especially with respect to the economy, climate change and public health.

Climate change and malaria

“Climate can influence malaria directly, by affecting transmission dynamics through vector and parasite development, or indirectly, via its influence on socioeconomic systems and other processes relevant to malaria infection, control and elimination.” So opens an accompanying paper (Nissan H et al, 2017) authored by the PAHO/WHO Collaborating centre on early warning systems for malaria and other climate sensitive diseases. The paper discusses climate forecasting, malaria modelling and the challenges of understanding the interactions between the two before considering the direct effects of climate variability and climate change (in particular, temperature and rainfall) on malaria transmission. Analyses from Latin America, East Africa and India illustrate the temporal variability across timescales and a study from Ethiopia illustrates the value of high quality climate data in distinguishing ENSO impacts from longer term trends. A particularly innovative section then explores some potential indirect effects of climate change on malaria, for example through extreme weather events disrupting supply chains, warmer temperatures discouraging the use of mosquito nets, and the effects of climate change on economic productivity and consequent levels of investment in malaria control.

We all recognise natural patterns of climate variability, for example on a day-to-day or seasonal timescale, and day-to-day, season-to-season, inter-annual and decadal variability in those patterns. We also increasingly appreciate that these fluctuations are superimposed onto long-term trends resulting from human-induced climate change. The authors warn against an eradication strategy which focuses exclusively on long-term trends; a failure to recognise natural variability on other timescales could increase the vulnerability of populations to climate. In a sobering assessment of the limitations of climate modelling to provide specific information around absolute values of temperature or rainfall for specific time periods, especially on the decadal to multi-decadal timescale, the authors explain the challenges of longer-term forecasting of the effects of climate change on anything smaller than a global or, at best, continental scale. More granular forecasts in time and space will require expert judgement based on a thorough evaluation of available projections for the region, timescale and application of interest. The paper concludes with a series of recommendations, including the need for adequate investment in climate and malaria surveillance systems, capacity building which allows the malaria community to make effective use of climate information, and encouragement that a structured approach be developed to integrate climate considerations into malaria eradication strategies.

Climate trends, malaria trends: understanding impact and identifying opportunities

Figure 7, described in more detail in Nissan H et al (2017) and Thomson M et al (2017), draws attention to the need to recognise underlying patterns of inter-annual climate variability when interpreting malaria trends.

The Weighted Anomaly Standardized Precipitation (WASP) data is from Tanzania and indicates periods in brown where rainfall was below the baseline average and malaria transmission may have been naturally compromised. In contrast, the green periods indicate

rainfall above the baseline average where malaria transmission is likely to have been encouraged. The timing of interventions is indicated in the figure. It is apparent that disregard for underlying climatic variations may result in under- or over-estimation of the impact of different control strategies. Conversely, the ability to anticipate periods of reduced suitability for transmission could be harnessed when considering the timing of efforts to interrupt transmission in a setting.

Figure 7: Tanzania ENACTS weighted anomaly standardized precipitation (WASP) index data. Brown indicates time where rainfall was below the baseline average, green indicates rainfall was above the baseline average. The WASP analysis is overlaid with the timing of interventions described in detail elsewhere. (See Thomson et al, 2017).

Other aspects of climate and health

Climate change and death

An empirical statistical model has been developed to relate temperature, precipitation and GDP per capita to the likely geographic limits of malaria at different time points (WHO, 2014, Béguin *et al*, 2011). Standard scenario-based projections of climate, economic development and population were then used to estimate potential changes in the population at risk of malaria in 2030 and 2050. To calculate mortality associated with malaria infections, national estimates of malaria mortality were multiplied by the national ratio of the projected population at risk to the estimated population at risk at the time of the study.

The model does not explicitly consider additional factors or interactions between the parameters included, e.g. climate change and economic development, although the authors

recognise that climate change adaptations such as changes in land use, disease and vector control, are likely to be highly associated with socioeconomic development. The model was also imperfect at predicting the extent of malaria transmission, for instance failing to identify areas currently at risk of malaria in southern sub-Saharan Africa. The authors also caution that per capita GDP may not be a useful proxy for socioeconomic factors affecting malaria risk in the future because of the complex, bidirectional interactions between malaria and development. Nevertheless, several conclusions are worthy of mention.

Firstly, projections of GDP per capita were considered more uncertain than those for temperature or precipitation changes.

Secondly, when only economic forecasts were taken into account, the model predicted a shrinking of malaria endemic areas. Much of the world, with the notable exception of Africa, was projected to become malaria free by the 2050s.

Thirdly, the converse was true when only climate variables were considered, with increases in malaria seen predominantly at the borders of current transmission zones (especially at the northern border of transmission in Africa, but also marked increases in South America and Asia by the 2050s). The influence of climate on malaria transmission was particularly marked in countries where GDP per capita was less than US\$ 20 000.

Fourthly, when simultaneous changes in GDP and climate were modelled, malaria was predicted to shrink by the 2050s.

Bringing climate and health closer together

The World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and the World Health Organization (WHO) are working jointly to develop the partnerships, research and applications, needed to improve the health sector's preparedness for climate and weather associated phenomena. The joint WMO-WHO office has produced a series of case studies (WMO-WHO, 2016) which illustrate the potential benefits of improving public health decision-making in the context of climate.

A number of case studies either focus on or have implications for malaria.

- Europe: an integrated monitoring system provides open-access information on past, present, and future environmental suitability for disease. This is actively used across the European Union and guided the public health response to local malaria transmission in Greece between 2009-2012.
- Ethiopia: In Ethiopia, a long-term collaboration between the Ministry of Health and the National Meteorological Agency informs malaria prevention and control. The value of climate information for epidemic forecasting and early case detection has been shown and resulted in the Ministry of Health supporting the National Meteorological Agency to improve meteorological observation infrastructure and data management systems.

- Ethiopia: An Epidemic Prognosis Incorporating Disease and Environmental Monitoring for Integrated Assessment (EPIDEMIA) system was developed to forecast the timing and locations of malaria epidemics and to facilitate the targeting of resources for malaria control.
- Solomon islands: Malaria transmission suitability maps are developed for the provincial level, based on in-situ and remotely sensed environmental, population and entomological indicators. A dry-season forecast produced for the malaria control programme informs them when and if rainfall will reach a threshold that favours transmission. The forecast is available 4 months in advance and updated monthly.
- Tanzania: Enhancing National Climate Services (ENACTS) produces quality assured, high-resolution climate data and products for mapping populations at risk of malaria. The national malaria program has used the products to understand the seasonality and optimal timing of interventions, to target resources, and evaluate the effectiveness of malaria interventions.
- Uganda: a malaria early warning system uses seasonal forecasts to drive a dynamic malaria model. The system produces skilful predictions four months in advance, providing potential for advanced action to protect over half the Ugandan population.

An emerging theme is the importance of integrated forecasts which link early warning systems that use remotely-sensed climate data to the early detection of malaria epidemics based on epidemiological surveillance. Common challenges include: a lack of in-country human capacity, increasing the challenge of sustainability; inadequate technical infrastructure (e.g. reliable internet connection); and issues related to data sharing policies.

Land use changes and malaria

A paper being prepared on this topic is outlined below.

Changing land use:

1. Land use/ land cover (LULC) change
 - a. Extent of LULC change
 - i. Definitions of land change (Turner et al., 2007)
 - ii. Anthropocene – transformation of terrestrial biome to anthropogenic biomes: (Ellis et al., 2010, Foley et al., 2005, Goldewijk et al., 2010)
 - b. Impacts on infectious disease transmission (Lambin et al., 2010, Patz et al., 2004, Jones et al., 2008, Jones et al., 2013, Gottdenker et al., 2014)
 - c. Impacts specifically on malaria transmission (Guerra et al., 2006, Yasuoka and Levins, 2007)
2. Drivers and global hotspots of anthropogenic land use change
 - a. Tropical deforestation (Gibbs et al., 2010, Hansen et al., 2008, Hansen et al., 2013, Rudel et al., 2009)
 - b. Agricultural expansion (Ramankutty et al., 2008, Brando et al., 2013)
 - c. Urbanisation and expansion of human settlements (Ellis and Ramankutty, 2008, Lloyd et al., 2017)

Land use and malaria transmission:

3. Vector biology and LULC
 - a. Physical changes to environment (such as changes in vegetation, microclimate and soil) and impacts on species composition and abundance of vector populations
 - i. Deforestation resulting in increased larval breeding sites in Amazon (Vittor et al., 2009)
 - ii. Types of agricultural (i.e. rubber plantations and rice paddies) associated with increases in anopheles densities (Tangena et al., 2016, Yasuoka and Levins, 2007)
 - iii. Effects of irrigation (Leonardo et al., 2005, Patz et al., 2004, Keiser et al., 2005a)
 - iv. Changes in vector habitat suitability between intact and disturbed forests (Brant et al., 2016, Loaiza et al., 2017)
 - v. Initial decreases in vector densities followed by colonisation of areas by more efficient vectors following deforestation (Guerra et al., 2006, Durnez et al., 2013)
 - vi. Reductions of malaria due to environmental management (Keiser et al., 2005b)
 - b. Ecological changes and vector biology (Ferguson et al., 2010)
 - i. Decreases in biodiversity with mixed effects on VBD disease transmission (Randolph and Dobson, 2012, Laporta et al., 2013)
 - ii. Changes to community structures – availability of blood meals and presence or absence of predators (LoGiudice et al., 2003, Nah et al., 2010)

- iii. Impact of habitat on vector behaviour in Southeast Asia (Trung et al., 2005)
- 4. Human populations
 - a. Population at risk
 - i. Influx of populations into endemic areas (Pindolia et al., 2014, Barbieri et al., 2005)
 - ii. Population migration between areas of different malaria endemicity (Wesolowski et al., 2012)
 - b. Local human movements and risk behaviours
 - i. Migrant worker populations – examples in Amazon and SE Asia (Wai et al., 2014, Satitvipawee et al., 2012, Singhanetra-Renard, 1993)
 - ii. Occupational changes – such as deforestation or extraction activities bringing people into vector habitats (Basurko et al., 2013, de Castro et al., 2006)
 - c. Accessibility of malaria control strategies
 - i. Remote populations and access to health care
 - ii. Increased socioeconomic status following land use change/ agricultural development reducing malaria risk (Tusting et al., 2013)
 - 1. Development and changes to housing structure (Tusting et al., 2015, Tusting et al., 2017)
- 5. Wildlife reservoirs (review of zoonotic malaria: (Ramasamy, 2014))
 - a. *P. knowlesi* in Southeast Asia
 - i. Initial reports and risk mapping of knowlesi (Singh et al., 2004, Shearer et al., 2016)
 - ii. Genetic evidence of zoonotic transmission – primarily from macaques to people (Lee et al., 2011, Assefa et al., 2015)
 - iii. Modelling studies – effects of land use change, contact between macaques and people and vector preferences on disease transmission (Imai et al., 2014, Yakob et al., 2010)
 - iv. Other zoonotic malaria from primates in Asia – *P. cynomologi* (Ta et al., 2014)
 - b. *P. simium* and *P. brasilianum* in South America (Brasil et al., 2017, Guimaraes et al., 2012)
 - c. Other primate hosts
 - i. Malaria infections in great apes and gorillas in West and Central Africa (Boundenga et al., 2015, Sundararaman et al., 2013)
 - ii. Origin of human malarias from non-human primates (Liu et al., 2010)

***P. knowlesi* case study**

This is available: please see separate document

Approaches to monitor

6. Risk factors
 - a. Identification of associations between LULC and disease – examples
 - i. Meta-analysis of deforestation and malaria epidemiology (Guerra et al., 2006, Yasuoka and Levins, 2007)
 - ii. Influence of deforestation, logging and fire in Brazilian Amazon (Hahn et al., 2014)
 - iii. Effects of deforestation on zoonotic malaria (Fornace et al., 2016, Moyes et al., 2016)
 - b. Importance of spatial and temporal scales and interactions with other environmental and demographic factors (Vanwambeke et al., 2007, Vanwambeke et al., 2006, Brock et al., 2016, Cohen et al., 2016)
 - c. Land use configuration – effects of fragmentation of vector ecology and disease risks (Brearley et al., 2013, Hutchings et al., 2011)
 - i. Non-malaria examples of fragmentation on VBD risks (Allan et al., 2003, Kiffner et al., 2010, LoGiudice et al., 2003, Ogrzewalska et al., 2011, Simon et al., 2014, Tran and Waller, 2013)
 - d. Risk mapping incorporating LULC factors (Clements et al., 2013), Malaria Atlas Project
7. Remote sensing
 - a. Satellite-based remote sensing methods
 - i. Active monitoring of deforestation – Global Forest Watch (<http://www.globalforestwatch.org/>), (Hansen et al., 2013)
 - ii. Associations between vegetation indices and malaria (Hay et al., 1998, Liu and Chen, 2006, Lourenco et al., 2011, Wayant et al., 2010)
 - iii. Other commercial and government sources of RS data (Gebreslasie, 2015, Hamm et al., 2015, Hay, 2000)
 - b. UAVs and aerial technology to map fine scale land cover changes (Fornace et al., 2014)

References

- ALLAN, B. F., KEESING, F. & OSTFELD, R. S. 2003. Effect of forest fragmentation on Lyme Disease risk. *Conservation Biology*, 17, 267-272.
- ASSEFA, S., LIM, C., PRESTON, M. D., DUFFY, C. W., NAIR, M. B., ADROUB, S. A., KADIR, K. A., GOLDBERG, J. M., NEAFSEY, D. E., DIVIS, P., CLARK, T. G., DURAISINGH, M. T., CONWAY, D. J., PAIN, A. & SINGH, B. 2015. Population genomic structure and adaptation in the zoonotic malaria parasite *Plasmodium knowlesi*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 112, 13027-32.
- BARBIERI, A. F., SAWYER, I. O. & SOARES-FILHO, B. S. 2005. Population and Land Use Effects on Malaria Prevalence in the Southern Brazilian Amazon. *Human Ecology*, 33, 847-874.
- BASURKO, C., DEMATTEI, C., HAN-SZE, R., GRENIER, C., JOUBERT, M., NACHER, M. & CARME, B. 2013. Deforestation, agriculture and farm jobs: a good recipe for *Plasmodium vivax* in French Guiana. *Malar J*, 12, 90.
- BOUNDENGA, L., OLOMO, B., ROUGERON, V., MOUELE, L. Y., MVE-ONDO, B., DELICAT-LOEMBET, L. M., MOUKODOUM, N. D., OKOUGA, A. P., ARNATHAU, C., ELGUERO, E., DURAND, P., LIEGEOIS, F., BOUE, V., MOTSCH, P., LE FLOHIC, G., NDOUNGOUE, A., PAUPY, C., BA, C. T., RENAUD, F. & PRUGNOLLE, F. 2015. Diversity of malaria parasites in great apes in Gabon. *Malar J*, 14, 111.
- BRANDO, P. M., COE, M. T., DEFRIES, R. & AZEVEDO, A. A. 2013. Ecology, economy and management of an agroindustrial frontier landscape in the southeast Amazon. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci*, 368, 20120152.
- BRANT, H. L., EWERS, R. M., VYTHILINGAM, I., DRAKELEY, C., BENEDICK, S. & MUMFORD, J. D. 2016. Vertical stratification of adult mosquitoes (Diptera: Culicidae) within a tropical rainforest in Sabah, Malaysia. *Malar J*, 15, 370.
- BRASIL, P., ZALIS, M. G., DE PINA-COSTA, A., SIQUEIRA, A. M., JUNIOR, C. B., SILVA, S., AREAS, A. L. L., PELAJO-MACHADO, M., DE ALVARENGA, D. A. M., DA SILVA SANTELLI, A. C. F., ALBUQUERQUE, H. G., CRAVO, P., SANTOS DE ABREU, F. V., PETERKA, C. L., ZANINI, G. M., SUAREZ MUTIS, M. C., PISSINATTI, A., LOURENCO-DE-OLIVEIRA, R., DE BRITO, C. F. A., DE FATIMA FERREIRA-DA-CRUZ, M., CULLETON, R. & DANIEL-RIBEIRO, C. T. 2017. Outbreak of human malaria caused by *Plasmodium simium* in the Atlantic Forest in Rio de Janeiro: a molecular epidemiological investigation. *Lancet Glob Health*, 5, e1038-e1046.
- BREARLEY, G., RHODES, J., BRADLEY, A., BAXTER, G., SEABROOK, L., LUNNEY, D., LIU, Y. & MCALPINE, C. 2013. Wildlife disease prevalence in human-modified landscapes. *Biol Rev Camb Philos Soc*, 88, 427-42.
- BROCK, P. M., FORNACE, K. M., PARMITER, M., COX, J., DRAKELEY, C. J., FERGUSON, H. M. & KAO, R. R. 2016. *Plasmodium knowlesi* transmission: integrating quantitative approaches from epidemiology and ecology to understand malaria as a zoonosis. *Parasitology*, 143, 389-400.
- CLEMENTS, A. C., REID, H. L., KELLY, G. C. & HAY, S. I. 2013. Further shrinking the malaria map: how can geospatial science help to achieve malaria elimination? *Lancet Infect Dis*, 13, 709-18.
- COHEN, J. M., CIVITELLO, D. J., BRACE, A. J., FEICHTINGER, E. M., ORTEGA, C. N., RICHARDSON, J. C., SAUER, E. L., LIU, X. & ROHR, J. R. 2016. Spatial scale modulates the strength of ecological processes driving disease distributions. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 113, E3359-64.
- DE CASTRO, M. C., MONTE-MOR, R. L., SAWYER, D. O. & SINGER, B. H. 2006. Malaria risk on the Amazon frontier. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 103, 2452-7.

- DURNEZ, L., MAO, S., DENIS, L., ROELANTS, P., SOCHANATHA, T. & COOSEMANS, M. 2013. Outdoor malaria transmission in forested villages of Cambodia. *Malar J*, 12, 329.
- ELLIS, E. C., GOLDEWIJK, K. K., SIEBERT, S., LIGHTMAN, D. & RAMANKUTTY, N. 2010. Anthropogenic transformation of the biomes, 1700 to 2000. *Global Ecology and Biogeography: A Journal of Macroecology*, 19, 589-606.
- ELLIS, E. C. & RAMANKUTTY, N. 2008. Putting people on the map: anthropogenic biomes of the world. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 6, 439-447.
- FERGUSON, H. M., DORNHAUS, A., BEECHE, A., BORGEMEISTER, C., GOTTLIEB, M., MULLA, M. S., GIMNIG, J. E., FISH, D. & KILLEEN, G. F. 2010. Ecology: a prerequisite for malaria elimination and eradication. *PLoS Med*, 7, e1000303.
- FOLEY, J. A., DEFRIES, R., ASNER, G. P., BARFORD, C., BONAN, G., CARPENTER, S. R., CHAPIN, F. S., COE, M. T., DAILY, G. C., GIBBS, H. K., HELKOWSKI, J. H., HOLLOWAY, T., HOWARD, E. A., KUCHARIK, C. J., MONFREDA, C., PATZ, J. A., PRENTICE, I. C., RAMANKUTTY, N. & SNYDER, P. K. 2005. Global consequences of land use. *Science*, 309, 570-4.
- FORNACE, K. M., ABIDIN, T. R., ALEXANDER, N., BROCK, P., GRIGG, M. J., MURPHY, A., WILLIAM, T., MENON, J., DRAKELEY, C. J. & COX, J. 2016. Association between Landscape Factors and Spatial Patterns of Plasmodium knowlesi Infections in Sabah, Malaysia. *Emerg Infect Dis*, 22, 201-9.
- FORNACE, K. M., DRAKELEY, C. J., WILLIAM, T., ESPINO, F. & COX, J. 2014. Mapping infectious disease landscapes: unmanned aerial vehicles and epidemiology. *Trends Parasitol*, 30, 514-519.
- GEBRESLASIE, M. T. 2015. A review of spatial technologies with applications for malaria transmission modelling and control in Africa. *Geospat Health*, 10, 328.
- GIBBS, H. K., RUESCH, A. S., ACHARD, F., CLAYTON, M. K., HOLMGREN, P., RAMANKUTTY, N. & FOLEY, J. A. 2010. Tropical forests were the primary sources of new agricultural land in the 1980s and 1990s. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 107, 16732-7.
- GOLDEWIJK, K. K., BEUSEN, A., VAN DRECHT, G. & DE VOS, M. 2010. The HYDE 3.1 spatially explicit database of human-induced global land use change over the past 12,000 years. *Global Ecology and Biogeography: A Journal of Macroecology*, 20, 73-86.
- GOTTDENKER, N. L., STREICKER, D. G., FAUST, C. L. & CARROLL, C. R. 2014. Anthropogenic land use change and infectious diseases: a review of the evidence. *Ecohealth*, 11, 619-32.
- GUERRA, C. A., SNOW, R. W. & HAY, S. I. 2006. A global assessment of closed forests, deforestation and malaria risk. *Ann Trop Med Parasitol*, 100, 189-204.
- GUIMARAES, L. O., BAJAY, M. M., WUNDERLICH, G., BUENO, M. G., ROHE, F., CATAO-DIAS, J. L., NEVES, A., MALAFRONTA, R. S., CURADO, I. & KIRCHGATTER, K. 2012. The genetic diversity of Plasmodium malariae and Plasmodium brasilianum from human, simian and mosquito hosts in Brazil. *Acta Trop*, 124, 27-32.
- HAHN, M. B., GANGNON, R. E., BARCELLOS, C., ASNER, G. P. & PATZ, J. A. 2014. Influence of deforestation, logging, and fire on malaria in the Brazilian Amazon. *PLoS One*, 9, e85725.
- HAMM, N. A., SOARES MAGALHAES, R. J. & CLEMENTS, A. C. 2015. Earth Observation, Spatial Data Quality, and Neglected Tropical Diseases. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*, 9, e0004164.
- HANSEN, M. C., POTAPOV, P. V., MOORE, R., HANCHER, M., TURUBANOVA, S. A., TYUKAVINA, A., THAU, D., STEHMAN, S. V., GOETZ, S. J., LOVELAND, T. R., KOMMAREDDY, A., EGOROV, A., CHINI, L., JUSTICE, C. O. & TOWNSHEND, J. R. 2013. High-resolution global maps of 21st-century forest cover change. *Science*, 342, 850-3.

- HANSEN, M. C., STEHMAN, S. V., POTAPOV, P. V., LOVELAND, T. R., TOWNSHEND, J. R., DEFRIES, R. S., PITTMAN, K. W., ARUNARWATI, B., STOLLE, F., STEININGER, M. K., CARROLL, M. & DIMICELI, C. 2008. Humid tropical forest clearing from 2000 to 2005 quantified by using multitemporal and multiresolution remotely sensed data. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 105, 9439-44.
- HAY, S. I. 2000. An overview of remote sensing and geodesy for epidemiology and public health application. *Adv Parasitol*, 47, 1-35.
- HAY, S. I., SNOW, R. W. & ROGERS, D. J. 1998. Predicting malaria seasons in Kenya using multitemporal meteorological satellite sensor data. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg*, 92, 12-20.
- HUTCHINGS, R. S., SALLUM, M. A. & HUTCHINGS, R. W. 2011. Mosquito (Diptera: Culicidae) diversity of a forest-fragment mosaic in the Amazon rain forest. *J Med Entomol*, 48, 173-87.
- IMAI, N., WHITE, M. T., GHANI, A. C. & DRAKELEY, C. J. 2014. Transmission and control of Plasmodium knowlesi: a mathematical modelling study. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*, 8, e2978.
- JONES, B. A., GRACE, D., KOCK, R., ALONSO, S., RUSHTON, J., SAID, M. Y., MCKEEVER, D., MUTUA, F., YOUNG, J., MCDERMOTT, J. & PFEIFFER, D. U. 2013. Zoonosis emergence linked to agricultural intensification and environmental change. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 110, 8399-404.
- JONES, K. E., PATEL, N. G., LEVY, M. A., STOREYGARD, A., BALK, D., GITTLEMAN, J. L. & DASZAK, P. 2008. Global trends in emerging infectious diseases. *Nature*, 451, 990-3.
- KEISER, J., DE CASTRO, M. C., MALTESE, M. F., BOS, R., TANNER, M., SINGER, B. H. & UTZINGER, J. 2005a. Effect of irrigation and large dams on the burden of malaria on a global and regional scale. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*, 72, 392-406.
- KEISER, J., SINGER, B. H. & UTZINGER, J. 2005b. Reducing the burden of malaria in different eco-epidemiological settings with environmental management: a systematic review. *Lancet Infect Dis*, 5, 695-708.
- KIFFNER, C., ZUCCHINI, W., SCHOMAKER, P., VOR, T., HAGEDORN, P., NIEDRIG, M. & RUHE, F. 2010. Determinants of tick-borne encephalitis in counties of southern Germany, 2001-2008. *Int J Health Geogr*, 9, 42.
- LAMBIN, E. F., TRAN, A., VANWAMBEKE, S. O., LINARD, C. & SOTI, V. 2010. Pathogenic landscapes: interactions between land, people, disease vectors, and their animal hosts. *Int J Health Geogr*, 9, 54.
- LAPORTA, G. Z., LOPEZ DE PRADO, P. I., KRAENKEL, R. A., COUTINHO, R. M. & SALLUM, M. A. 2013. Biodiversity can help prevent malaria outbreaks in tropical forests. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*, 7, e2139.
- LEE, K. S., DIVIS, P. C., ZAKARIA, S. K., MATUSOP, A., JULIN, R. A., CONWAY, D. J., COX-SINGH, J. & SINGH, B. 2011. Plasmodium knowlesi: reservoir hosts and tracking the emergence in humans and macaques. *PLoS Pathog*, 7, e1002015.
- LEONARDO, L. R., RIVERA, P. T., CRISOSTOMO, B. A., SAROL, J. N., BANTAYAN, N. C., TIU, W. U. & BERGQUIST, N. R. 2005. A study of the environmental determinants of malaria and schistosomiasis in the Philippines using Remote Sensing and Geographic Information Systems. *Parassitologia*, 47, 105-14.
- LIU, J. & CHEN, X. P. 2006. Relationship of remote sensing normalized differential vegetation index to Anopheles density and malaria incidence rate. *Biomed Environ Sci*, 19, 130-2.
- LIU, W., LI, Y., LEARN, G. H., RUDICELL, R. S., ROBERTSON, J. D., KEELE, B. F., NDJANGO, J. B., SANZ, C. M., MORGAN, D. B., LOCATELLI, S., GONDER, M. K., KRANZUSCH, P. J., WALSH, P. D., DELAPORTE, E., MPOUDI-NGOLE, E., GEORGIEV, A. V., MULLER, M. N.,

- SHAW, G. M., PEETERS, M., SHARP, P. M., RAYNER, J. C. & HAHN, B. H. 2010. Origin of the human malaria parasite *Plasmodium falciparum* in gorillas. *Nature*, 467, 420-5.
- LLOYD, C. T., SORICHETTA, A. & TATEM, A. J. 2017. High resolution global gridded data for use in population studies. *Sci Data*, 4, 170001.
- LOAIZA, J. R., DUTARI, L. C., ROVIRA, J. R., SANJUR, O. I., LAPORTA, G. Z., PECOR, J., FOLEY, D. H., EASTWOOD, G., KRAMER, L. D., RADTKE, M. & PONGSIRI, M. 2017. Disturbance and mosquito diversity in the lowland tropical rainforest of central Panama. *Sci Rep*, 7, 7248.
- LOGIUDICE, K., OSTFELD, R. S., SCHMIDT, K. A. & KEESING, F. 2003. The ecology of infectious disease: effects of host diversity and community composition on Lyme disease risk. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 100, 567-71.
- LOURENCO, P. M., SOUSA, C. A., SEIXAS, J., LOPES, P., NOVO, M. T. & ALMEIDA, A. P. 2011. Anopheles atroparvus density modeling using MODIS NDVI in a former malarious area in Portugal. *J Vector Ecol*, 36, 279-91.
- MOYES, C. L., SHEARER, F. M., HUANG, Z., WIEBE, A., GIBSON, H. S., NIJMAN, V., MOHD-AZLAN, J., BRODIE, J. F., MALAIVIJITNOND, S., LINKIE, M., SAMEJIMA, H., O'BRIEN, T. G., TRAINOR, C. R., HAMADA, Y., GIORDANO, A. J., KINNAIRD, M. F., ELYAZAR, I. R., SINKA, M. E., VYTHILINGAM, I., BANGS, M. J., PIGOTT, D. M., WEISS, D. J., GOLDING, N. & HAY, S. I. 2016. Predicting the geographical distributions of the macaque hosts and mosquito vectors of *Plasmodium knowlesi* malaria in forested and non-forested areas. *Parasit Vectors*, 9, 242.
- NAH, K., KIM, Y. & LEE, J. M. 2010. The dilution effect of the domestic animal population on the transmission of *P. vivax* malaria. *J Theor Biol*, 266, 299-306.
- OGRZEWALSKA, M., UEZU, A., JENKINS, C. N. & LABRUNA, M. B. 2011. Effect of forest fragmentation on tick infestations of birds and tick infection rates by rickettsia in the Atlantic forest of Brazil. *Ecohealth*, 8, 320-31.
- PATZ, J. A., DASZAK, P., TABOR, G. M., AGUIRRE, A. A., PEARL, M., EPSTEIN, J., WOLFE, N. D., KILPATRICK, A. M., FOUFOPOULOS, J., MOLYNEUX, D., BRADLEY, D. J., WORKING GROUP ON LAND USE, C. & DISEASE, E. 2004. Unhealthy landscapes: Policy recommendations on land use change and infectious disease emergence. *Environ Health Perspect*, 112, 1092-8.
- PINDOLIA, D. K., GARCIA, A. J., HUANG, Z., FIK, T., SMITH, D. L. & TATEM, A. J. 2014. Quantifying cross-border movements and migrations for guiding the strategic planning of malaria control and elimination. *Malar J*, 13, 169.
- RAMANKUTTY, N., EVAN, A. T., MONFREDA, C. & FOLEY, J. A. 2008. Farming the planet: 1. Geographic distribution of global agricultural lands in the year 2000. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*, 22.
- RAMASAMY, R. 2014. Zoonotic malaria - global overview and research and policy needs. *Front Public Health*, 2, 123.
- RANDOLPH, S. E. & DOBSON, A. D. 2012. Pangloss revisited: a critique of the dilution effect and the biodiversity-buffers-disease paradigm. *Parasitology*, 139, 847-63.
- RUDEL, T. K., DEFRIES, R., ASNER, G. P. & LAURANCE, W. F. 2009. Changing drivers of deforestation and new opportunities for conservation. *Conserv Biol*, 23, 1396-405.
- SATITVIPAWEE, P., WONGKHANG, W., PATTANASIN, S., HOITHONG, P. & BHUMIRATANA, A. 2012. Predictors of malaria-association with rubber plantations in Thailand. *BMC Public Health*, 12, 1115.
- SHEARER, F. M., HUANG, Z., WEISS, D. J., WIEBE, A., GIBSON, H. S., BATTLE, K. E., PIGOTT, D. M., BRADY, O. J., PUTAPORNTIP, C., JONGWUTIWES, S., LAU, Y. L., MANSKE, M., AMATO, R., ELYAZAR, I. R., VYTHILINGAM, I., BHATT, S., GETHING, P. W., SINGH, B.,

- GOLDING, N., HAY, S. I. & MOYES, C. L. 2016. Estimating Geographical Variation in the Risk of Zoonotic *Plasmodium knowlesi* Infection in Countries Eliminating Malaria. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*, 10, e0004915.
- SIMON, J. A., MARROTTE, R. R., DESROSIERS, N., FISET, J., GAITAN, J., GONZALEZ, A., KOFFI, J. K., LAPOINTE, F. J., LEIGHTON, P. A., LINDSAY, L. R., LOGAN, T., MILORD, F., OGDEN, N. H., ROGIC, A., ROY-DUFRESNE, E., SUTER, D., TESSIER, N. & MILLIEN, V. 2014. Climate change and habitat fragmentation drive the occurrence of *Borrelia burgdorferi*, the agent of Lyme disease, at the northeastern limit of its distribution. *Evol Appl*, 7, 750-64.
- SINGH, B., KIM SUNG, L., MATUSOP, A., RADHAKRISHNAN, A., SHAMSUL, S. S., COX-SINGH, J., THOMAS, A. & CONWAY, D. J. 2004. A large focus of naturally acquired *Plasmodium knowlesi* infections in human beings. *Lancet*, 363, 1017-24.
- SINGHANETRA-RENARD, A. 1993. Malaria and mobility in Thailand. *Soc Sci Med*, 37, 1147-54.
- SUNDARARAMAN, S. A., LIU, W., KEELE, B. F., LEARN, G. H., BITTINGER, K., MOUACHA, F., AHUKA-MUNDEKE, S., MANSKE, M., SHERRILL-MIX, S., LI, Y., MALENKE, J. A., DELAPORTE, E., LAURENT, C., MPOUDI NGOLE, E., KWIATKOWSKI, D. P., SHAW, G. M., RAYNER, J. C., PEETERS, M., SHARP, P. M., BUSHMAN, F. D. & HAHN, B. H. 2013. *Plasmodium falciparum*-like parasites infecting wild apes in southern Cameroon do not represent a recurrent source of human malaria. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 110, 7020-5.
- TA, T. H., HISAM, S., LANZA, M., JIRAM, A. I., ISMAIL, N. & RUBIO, J. M. 2014. First case of a naturally acquired human infection with *Plasmodium cynomolgi*. *Malar J*, 13, 68.
- TANGENA, J. A., THAMMAVONG, P., WILSON, A. L., BREY, P. T. & LINDSAY, S. W. 2016. Risk and Control of Mosquito-Borne Diseases in Southeast Asian Rubber Plantations. *Trends Parasitol*, 32, 402-15.
- TRAN, P. M. & WALLER, L. 2013. Effects of landscape fragmentation and climate on Lyme disease incidence in the northeastern United States. *Ecohealth*, 10, 394-404.
- TRUNG, H. D., BORTEL, W. V., SOCHANATHA, T., KEOKENCHANH, K., BRIET, O. J. & COOSEMANS, M. 2005. Behavioural heterogeneity of *Anopheles* species in ecologically different localities in Southeast Asia: a challenge for vector control. *Trop Med Int Health*, 10, 251-62.
- TURNER, B. L., 2ND, LAMBIN, E. F. & REENBERG, A. 2007. The emergence of land change science for global environmental change and sustainability. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 104, 20666-71.
- TUSTING, L. S., BOTTOMLEY, C., GIBSON, H., KLEINSCHMIDT, I., TATEM, A. J., LINDSAY, S. W. & GETHING, P. W. 2017. Housing Improvements and Malaria Risk in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Multi-Country Analysis of Survey Data. *PLoS Med*, 14, e1002234.
- TUSTING, L. S., IPPOLITO, M. M., WILLEY, B. A., KLEINSCHMIDT, I., DORSEY, G., GOSLING, R. D. & LINDSAY, S. W. 2015. The evidence for improving housing to reduce malaria: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Malar J*, 14, 209.
- TUSTING, L. S., WILLEY, B., LUCAS, H., THOMPSON, J., KAFY, H. T., SMITH, R. & LINDSAY, S. W. 2013. Socioeconomic development as an intervention against malaria: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet*, 382, 963-72.
- VANWAMBEKE, S. O., LAMBIN, E. F., EICHHORN, M. P., FLASSE, S. P., HARBACH, R. E., OSKAM, L., SOMBOON, P., VAN BEERS, S., VAN BENTHEM, B. H. B., WALTON, C. & BUTLIN, R. K. 2007. Impact of Land-use Change on Dengue and Malaria in Northern Thailand. *EcoHealth*, 4, 37-51.

- VANWAMBEKE, S. O., VAN BENTHEM, B. H., KHANTIKUL, N., BURGHOORN-MAAS, C., PANART, K., OSKAM, L., LAMBIN, E. F. & SOMBOON, P. 2006. Multi-level analyses of spatial and temporal determinants for dengue infection. *Int J Health Geogr*, 5, 5.
- VITTOR, A. Y., PAN, W., GILMAN, R. H., TIELSCH, J., GLASS, G., SHIELDS, T., SANCHEZ-LOZANO, W., PINEDO, V. V., SALAS-COBOS, E., FLORES, S. & PATZ, J. A. 2009. Linking deforestation to malaria in the Amazon: characterization of the breeding habitat of the principal malaria vector, *Anopheles darlingi*. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*, 81, 5-12.
- WAI, K. T., KYAW, M. P., OO, T., ZAW, P., NYUNT, M. H., THIDA, M. & KYAW, T. T. 2014. Spatial distribution, work patterns, and perception towards malaria interventions among temporary mobile/migrant workers in artemisinin resistance containment zone. *BMC Public Health*, 14, 463.
- WAYANT, N. M., MALDONADO, D., ROJAS DE ARIAS, A., COUSINO, B. & GOODIN, D. G. 2010. Correlation between normalized difference vegetation index and malaria in a subtropical rain forest undergoing rapid anthropogenic alteration. *Geospat Health*, 4, 179-90.
- WESOLOWSKI, A., EAGLE, N., TATEM, A. J., SMITH, D. L., NOOR, A. M., SNOW, R. W. & BUCKEE, C. O. 2012. Quantifying the impact of human mobility on malaria. *Science*, 338, 267-70.
- YAKOB, L., BONSALE, M. B. & YAN, G. 2010. Modelling knowlesi malaria transmission in humans: vector preference and host competence. *Malar J*, 9, 329.
- YASUOKA, J. & LEVINS, R. 2007. Impact of deforestation and agricultural development on anopheline ecology and malaria epidemiology. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*, 76, 450-60.

Migration

In 1961, RM Prothero drew attention to the challenge that population movements would present for malaria eradication efforts in Africa (Prothero R, 1961). The importance of migration in maintaining malaria transmission has therefore long been recognised but only limited progress has been made in understanding or overcoming the associated challenges. Since Prothero's day the picture has been complicated by increasing and now sustained high levels of air travel, major changes in geopolitics, new markets opening up (e.g. Chinese labourers, businessmen and tourists in Africa), and changes in the patterns of movement in response to disasters and climate change.

The importance of migration to malaria elimination is that parasites move with people. Movement of (possibly asymptotically) infected people into areas which have eliminated malaria but remain able to support transmission raises the spectre of reintroduction of the disease. Areas moving towards elimination have their progress impeded by inward migration of parasites from outside. For example, most of the malaria cases imported to the EMRO region are thought to be from Africa, again drawing attention to the importance of sustained control in Africa, and migrants from Pakistan and Afghanistan help maintain malaria transmission in the Arabian peninsular.

Specific risks related to malaria have been identified amongst migrant workers and mobile populations and are reviewed elsewhere.

In the context of malaria's mega trends, large scale migration is a small contributor to overall population change, compared with the changes in birth and death rates. Figure 8

shows annual net migration by world region between 1980 and 2015. The volume of net migration across the world's regions steadily increased until 2010, with a net inflow of migrants to Europe, North America and Oceania from Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, and Africa. At its peak, the total migrant flow reached 3.1 million migrants per year before reducing between 2010 – 2015. It seems likely that, as migration to high income countries becomes more difficult, migration flows between low and middle income countries, especially on the same continent, will increase.

Migration flows within malaria–endemic regions are likely to influence efforts to eliminate malaria but are harder to capture. Census-derived migration data is considered a good proxy for internal connectivity across temporal scales. An open access archive of internal migration flows in endemic countries has been developed (Sorichetta A et al, 2016). Estimated subnational migration flows are illustrated in figures 9-11 for malaria endemic countries of Africa, Asia and Latin America and the Caribbean, respectively.

Figure 9: Estimated internal human migration flows between subnational administrative units for every malaria endemic country in Africa

Figures 10 & 11: Estimated internal human migration flows between subnational administrative units for every malaria endemic country in Asia (top) and Latin America and the Caribbean (bottom)

Implications of migration for malaria control

Forecasts for migrations (other than rural to urban) and refugee populations are in general unreliable as these can be volatile in the short-term due to unforeseeable events. The development of approaches to track migration patterns is therefore of particular interest. New approaches to monitoring the movement of parasites and people (as a proxy for the parasite) include the use of air travel data and mobile phone tracer signals (Tatem A, 2014).

However, optimal approaches to the use of data on migration are yet to be defined. It is possible that an understanding of the scale and patterns of migration should feed into decisions about the scale of activities to eliminate malaria.

The distribution of molecular drug resistance alleles in *P. falciparum* has been used to highlight the importance of human migration on the distribution of malaria parasites (Pearce R et al, 2009). Mapping of DHPS resistance alleles strongly suggested that economic and transport infrastructures may govern parasite movement in Africa through their effect on the movement of people. The distribution of specific alleles broadly corresponded to economic communities (figure 12). Economic agreements during the 1990s between Gabon and Senegal may have favoured the migration of workers and thus help explain moderately high frequencies of specific alleles seen in the two countries in comparison with Gabon's neighbours.

The ease and impact of elimination efforts may be optimised when applied at a geographic scale that encompasses regions which exchange parasites. Coordinated campaigns within

economic areas may be more likely to succeed than campaigns within individual countries that constantly battle the risk of imported infections.

At the local level, understanding the factors which push and pull people in and out of malaria endemic areas – infrastructure and rural development, logging, farming, political movements, natural disasters - needs to be accompanied by advocacy and strengthened development of migrant health information systems to enable targeted malaria control to be made readily accessible to migrants (Jitthai N, 2013).

DRAFT

Conclusion

Mega trends in demography, urbanisation, climate change and migration have been presented, plus an outline of land use changes. Where possible, some assessment of the likely impact on malaria risk and implications for eradication has been discussed. This first contribution to the SAGme is intended to stimulate discussion, refinement and subsequent further exploration of key issues.

Given the imprecision surrounding estimates of any of the mega trends considered, it is not expected that efforts to integrate quantitative analyses would result in accurate or useful outputs.

It is already clear that Africa, the heartland of malaria today, will drive the global population changes in the coming decades and likely also key migration patterns of relevance to malaria. With enhanced access to health, education and opportunities to contribute to the economic growth of Africa, it is possible that the adverse effects of climate change on malaria risk may largely be averted. Innovations in climate and health science, and the links between them, should enable identification and amelioration of specific risks.

Population pressures increase the risk of civil unrest which makes malaria control more challenging. It is difficult to anticipate with any certainty where future emergencies, whether natural or man-made, will arise, but we can be confident that malaria eradication efforts will struggle in such areas just as smallpox and polio eradication efforts have done. There is a clear need therefore to engage systematically with malaria control in emergency settings and to develop approaches which are tailored for such fragile settings.

The SAGme is invited to suggest any additional mega trends of relevance to malaria, and topics worthy of further consideration in future versions of this document.

References

Angel S, Parent J, Civco DL, Blei AM. Making room for a planet of cities. Cambridge: Lincoln Institute of Land Policy; 2011.

https://www.citiesalliance.org/sites/citiesalliance.org/files/CA_Images/Making Room for a Planet of Cities.pdf.

Agyepong I, Sewankambo N, Binagwaho A, Coll-Seck A, Corrah T, Ezeh A, Fekadu A, Kilonzo N, Lamptey P, Masiye F, Mayosi B, Mboup S, Muyembe JJ, Pate M, Sidibe M, Simons B, Tlou S, Gheorghe A, Legido-Quigley H, McManus J, Ng E, O'Leary M, Enoch J, Kassebaum N, Piot P. The path to longer and healthier lives for all Africans by 2030: the Lancet Commission on the future of health in sub-Saharan Africa. *Lancet* 2017. Published online September 13, 2017 [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)31509-X](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)31509-X)

Ayeni B (1981). Lagos. Problems and Planning in Third World Cities. Pacione M (ed), Croom Helm, London. Pages 127-155.

Baird JK, Jones TR, Danudirgo EW, Annis BA, Bangs MJ, Basri H, Purnomo, Masbar S. Age-dependent acquired protection against *Plasmodium falciparum* in people having two years exposure to hyperendemic malaria. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 1991 Jul;45(1):65-76.

Baird JK, Purnomo, Basri H, Bangs MJ, Andersen EM, Jones TR, Masbar S, Harjosuwarno S, Subianto B, Arbani PR. Age-specific prevalence of *Plasmodium falciparum* among six populations with limited histories of exposure to endemic malaria. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 1993 Dec;49(6):707-19.

Beguín A, Hales S, Rocklöv J, Angström C, Louis V, Sauerborn R (2011). The opposing effects of climate change and socio-economic development on the global distribution of malaria. *Glob Environ Chang.* 21: 1209–14.

Carneiro I, Roca-Feltrer A, Griffin J, Smith L, Tanner M, Armstrong Schellenberg J, Greenwood B, Schellenberg D. Age-Patterns of Malaria vary with Severity, Transmission Intensity and Seasonality in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review and Pooled Analysis. *PLoS One*, 2010; 5(2):e8988.

De Silva P and Marshall J. Factors Contributing to Urban Malaria Transmission in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Tropical Medicine* Volume 2012. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2012/819563>

Drechsel P and Keraita B. (Eds.). 2014. Irrigated urban vegetable production in Ghana: characteristics, benefits and risk mitigation. 2nd ed. Colombo, Sri Lanka: International Water Management Institute (IWMI). 247 p. doi: 10.5337/2014.219.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2007). Legal notice on publication of the details of the breakdown of the National and State provisional totals 2006 census. Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette, 94:1-26. www.nigerianstat.gov.ng.

Fowkes FJ, Boeuf P, Beeson JG. Immunity to malaria in an era of declining malaria transmission. *Parasitology*. 2016 Feb;143(2):139-53. doi: 10.1017/S0031182015001249.

Frayne B, Pendleton W, Crush J, Acquah B, Battersby-Lennard J, Bras E et al. The state of urban food insecurity in Southern Africa. Kingston and Cape Town: Queen's University and African Food Security Urban Network; 2010.

Gómez K, Caicedo MA, Gaitán A, Herrera-Varela M, Arce M, Vallejo A, Padilla J, Chaparro J, Pacheco MA, Escalante A, Arevalo-Herrera M, Herrera S. Characterizing the malaria rural-to-urban transmission interface: The importance of reactive case detection. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis* 2017;11(7):e0005780. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal>.

Govoetchan R, Gnanguenon V, Azondékon R, Agossa RF, Sovi A, Oké-Agbo F, Ossè R, Akogbéto M, 2014. Evidence for perennial malaria in rural and urban areas under the Sudanian climate of Kandi, northeastern Benin. *Parasit Vectors* 7: 79.

Jennings R, Souza D, Todd JE, Armstrong M, Flanagan KL, Riley EM, Doherty JF. Imported *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria: are patients originating from disease-endemic areas less likely to develop severe disease? A prospective, observational study. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2006 Dec;75(6):1195-9.

Jitthai N. Migration and malaria. *Southeast Asian J Trop Med Public Health*. 2013;44 Suppl 1:166-200; discussion 306-7.

Kabaria C, Noor A, Linard C and Snow R. Impacts of urbanization on malaria parasite prevalence in Africa. PhD Thesis 2015. The Open University.

Kirby M, Ameh D, Bottomley C, Green C, Jawara M, Milligan PJ, Snell PC, Conway DJ, Lindsay SW. Effect of two different house screening interventions on exposure to malaria vectors and on anaemia in children in The Gambia: a randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2009 Sep 19;374(9694):998-1009. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(09)60871-0

Klinkenberg E, McCall PJ, Wilson M, Amerasinghe F and Donnelly M. Impact of urban agriculture on malaria vectors in Accra, Ghana. *Malar J*. 2008; 7: 151. doi: 10.1186/1475-2875-7-151

Leppo K, Ollila E, Peña S, Wismar M, Cook S, editors. Health in All Policies: seizing opportunities, implementing policies. Helsinki: Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, Finland; 2013 <http://www.euro.who.int/en/about-us/partners/observatory/publications/studies/health-in-all-policies-seizing-opportunities,-implementing-policies>

Marsh K, Kinyanjui S. Immune effector mechanisms in malaria. *Parasite Immunol*. 2006 Jan-Feb;28(1-2):51-60.

Measuring sprawl 2014. Washington DC: Smart Growth America; 2014. <http://www.smartgrowthamerica.org/documents/measuring-sprawl-2014.pdf>

Millennium Development Goals report 2015. New York: United Nations; 2015.
[www.un.org/millenniumgoals/2015_MDG_Report/pdf/MDG 2015 rev \(July 1\).pdf](http://www.un.org/millenniumgoals/2015_MDG_Report/pdf/MDG%202015%20rev%20(July%201).pdf)

Nankabirwa J, Brooker S, Clarke S, Fernando D, Gitonga C, Schellenberg D, Greenwood B. Malaria in school-age children in Africa: an increasingly important challenge. *TMIH* 2014;19 (11); 1294–1309. DOI: 10.1111/tmi.12374

Nissan, H., I. Ukawuba and M.C. Thomson (2017). Factoring Climate Change into Malaria Eradication Strategy. Technical Report to the Scientific Advisory Group for Malaria Eradication, Global Malaria Programme, World Health Organisation.

Obuobie E, Keraita B, Danso G, Amoah P, Olufunke O, Raschid-Sally L, Drechsel P. 2006. Irrigated urban vegetable production in Ghana: Characteristics, benefits and risks. Accra, Ghana: IWMI-RUAF-CPWF.

Omumbo JA, Guerra CA, Hay SI, Snow RW, 2005. The influence of urbanisation on measures of Plasmodium falciparum infection prevalence in east Africa. *Acta Trop* 93: 11–21.

Pearce RJ, Pota H, Evehe M-SB, Ba E-H, Mombo-Ngoma G, et al. (2009) Multiple Origins and Regional Dispersal of Resistant dhps in African Plasmodium falciparum Malaria. *PLoS Med* 6(4): e1000055. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed.1000055

Prothero R. Population movements and problems of malaria eradication in Africa. *Bull World Health Organ.* 1961;24:405-25.

Save the Children (2015). State of the world's mothers: the urban disadvantage. London: Save the Children; 2015
http://www.savethechildren.org/site/c.8rKLIXMGIpl4E/b.8585863/k.9F31/State_of_the_Worlds_Mothers.htm?msource=wenlpstw0515

Smith A, Bradley D, Smith V, Blaze M, Behrens R, Chiodini P, Whitty C. Imported malaria and high risk groups: observational study using UK surveillance data 1987-2006. *BMJ.* 2008 Jul 12; 337(7661): 103–106. doi: 10.1136/bmj.a120

Sorichetta A, Bird T, Ruktanonchai N, Erbach-Schoenberg E, Pezzulo C, Tejedor N, Waldoock I, Sadler J, Garcia A, Sedda L, Tatem A. Mapping internal connectivity through human migration in malaria endemic countries. *Sci Data.* 2016 Aug 16;3:160066. doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.66

State of the world's cities 2012/2013: prosperity of cities. New York: United Nations Human Settlements Programme; 2013.

Szreter S. Industrialization and health. *Br Med Bull.* 2004;69:75–86.
doi:10.1093/bmb/ldh005.

Tatem AJ, Gething PW, Smith DL, Hay SI, 2013. Urbanization and the global malaria recession. *Malar J* 12: 1–10.

Tatem A. Mapping population and pathogen movements. *Int Health*. 2014 Mar;6(1):5-11. doi: 10.1093/inthealth/ihu006.

Thomson, M.C. et al., 2017. Using Rainfall and Temperature Data in the Evaluation of National Malaria Control Programs in Africa. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, (Suppl. 3 : Malaria Impact Evaluation), pp.32–45.

Tusting L, Ippolito M, Willey B, Kleinschmidt I, Dorsey G, Gosling R, Lindsay S. (2015) The evidence for improving housing to reduce malaria: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Malaria Journal* 2015;14:209 doi.org/10.1186/s12936-015-0724-1

Tusting LS, Bottomley C, Gibson H, Kleinschmidt I, Tatem AJ, Lindsay SW, et al. (2017) Housing Improvements and Malaria Risk in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Multi-Country Analysis of Survey Data. *PLoS Med* 14(2): e1002234. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed.1002234

UNICEF (2012). The state of the world's children 2012: children in an urban world. New York: United Nations Children's Fund. http://www.unicef.org/sowc2012/pdfs/SOWC_2012-Main_Report_EN_13Mar2012.pdf

UNICEF (2015). Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS). New York: United Nations Children's Fund. <http://mics.unicef.org/>

United Nations (2012). World Urbanization Prospects: The 2011 Revision, New York: Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division: United Nations.

United Nations Data Revolution Group. (2014) A world that counts: mobilising the data revolution for sustainable development. New York. <http://www.undatarevolution.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/12/A-World-That-Counts2.pdf>

United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2017). World Population Prospects: The 2017 Revision, Key Findings and Advance Tables. Working Paper No. ESA/P/WP/248. Accessible at: https://esa.un.org/unpd/wpp/Publications/Files/WPP2017_KeyFindings.pdf

United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs. World urbanization prospects: the 2014 revision highlights. New York: United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division; 2014 <http://esa.un.org/unpd/wup/Highlights/WUP2014-Highlights.pdf>

United Nations Habitat. United Nations Human Settlements Programme. The economic role of cities. Nairobi 2011. <http://mirror.unhabitat.org/pmss/getElectronicVersion.aspx?nr=3260&alt=1>

Wang S, Lengeler C, Smith T, Vounatsou P, Cissé G, Diallo D, Akogbeto M, Mtasiwa D, Teklehaimanot A and Tanner M. Rapid urban malaria appraisal (RUMA) in sub-Saharan Africa. *Malaria Journal* 2005. 4:40. doi.org/10.1186/1475-2875-4-40

Wilson M, Krogstad D, Arinaitwe E, Arevalo-Herrera M, Chery L, Ferreira M, Ndiaye D, Mathanga D, Eapen A. Urban Malaria: Understanding its Epidemiology, Ecology, and Transmission across Seven Diverse ICEMR Network Sites. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2015 Sep 2; 93(3 Suppl): 110–123. doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.14-0834

WHO (2010). Hidden cities: unmasking and overcoming health inequities in urban settings. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2010.
http://www.who.int/kobe_centre/publications/hiddencities_media/who_un_habitat_hiddencities_web.pdf

WHO (2014). Quantitative risk assessment of the effects of climate change on selected causes of death, 2030s and 2050s. ISBN 978 92 4 150769 1.
<http://www.who.int/globalchange/publications/quantitative-risk-assessment/en/>

WHO (2015). Global health observatory, urban health. Geneva: World Health Organization; http://www.who.int/gho/urban_health/en/

WHO/WMO. (2016) Climate Services for Health: Improving public health decision-making in a new climate. Eds. J.Shumake-Guillemot and L.Fernandez-Montoya. Geneva.

Woetzel J, Ram S, Mischke J, Garemo N, Sankhe S. A blueprint for addressing the global affordable housing challenge. Seoul: McKinsey Global Institute; 2014
[http://globalhousingindicators.org/sites/globalhousingindicators.org/files/McKinsey Global Institute Full Report.pdf](http://globalhousingindicators.org/sites/globalhousingindicators.org/files/McKinsey%20Global%20Institute%20Full%20Report.pdf)

Yadouléton A, N'Guessan R, Allagbé H, Asidi A, Boko M, Osse R, Padonou G, Kindé G and Akogbéto M. Human Landing Catches (HLC) in households close to the vegetable farms and in others located far from the farms. *Parasites & Vectors* 2010;3:118.
doi.org/10.1186/1756-3305-3-118